

TECHNISCHE
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WIEN

Data management plan (DMP)

Effective implementation of the EPBD in line with short-term and long-term policy requirements

LIFE22-CET-EPBD.wise

Version	Effective date	Description of document/changes
1.0	14/12/2023	The first version of DMP – created for the start of the project (D1.1 – First draft)
2.0	31/03/2024	The second version of DMP – prepared for midterm review (D1.1 – Final Version)

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Start date	2023-09-30
End date	2026-06-29
Funder, funding programme, grant number	European Commission, Programme for the Environment and Climate Action (LIFE), Clean Energy Transition (LIFE), 101120194
Internal project number TU Wien	2258475

List of acronyms

DMP	data management plan
RDM	research data management
CSV	comma-separated values
DOI	digital objects identifiers
LTRS	long-term renovation strategies
BRP	building renovation passport
EPC	energy performance certificate
MEPS	minimum energy performance standards
DHW	domestic hot water
FC	focus countries

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Introduction

Science Europe practical guide, FAIR data

A DMP is a structured document that keeps a record of what research data is created and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions.

For writing this DMP, we followed [the recommendations of Science Europe](#)¹ as they reflect the guidelines agreed upon by the major funders in Europe.

To make our data FAIR, they generally will be treated according to the following criteria:

- We will make our data findable by uploading it to a data repository with a persistent identifier and adding relevant metadata.
- We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data wherever possible. In cases where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests.
- We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a common way within our domain using the same file formats, schemas, and vocabularies. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.
- We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published datasets. The descriptions include details on the methodology used and analytical and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked.

Relevant Policies and Guidelines

- TU Wien Policy for Research Data Management: <https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Policy%20for%20Research%20Data%20Management.pdf>
- TU Wien Code of Conduct – Rules to Ensure Good Scientific Practice: <https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Code%20of%20Conduct%20E2%80%93%20Rules%20to%20Ensure%20Good%20Scientific%20Practice.pdf>
- Directives and Regulations of the TU Wien Rectorate: <https://www.tuwien.at/en/tu-wien/organisation/central-divisions/data-protection-and-document-management/directives-regulations/>
- TU Wien Data Protection: <https://www.tuwien.at/en/tu-wien/organisation/central-divisions/data-protection-and-document-management/data-protection-at-tu-wien>

Information about the project

EPBD.wise, or "Effective implementation of the EPBD in line with short-term and long-term policy requirements," is a crucial initiative responding to the immediate need for intensified efforts in shaping and reinforcing building sector policies to meet evolving energy and climate objectives. The genesis of this project lies in the revised Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD), which brought forth pivotal elements such as zero-emission buildings (ZEB), national building renovation plans (NBRP), minimum energy performance standards (MEPS), and bolstered instruments like building renovation passports (BRP) and energy performance certificates (EPC).

Dedicated to the cause, EPBD.wise has set its sights on six Member States, including Hungary, Ukraine, Bulgaria, Greece, Poland, and Romania. The primary thrust is to assist public authorities in these

¹ 10.5281/ZENODO.4915861

countries in the effective crafting, execution, and assessment of instruments crucial to the EPBD, particularly the NBRP, MEPS, and EPC.

As a guiding light, the project takes a cohesive approach, aligning itself with the tenets of the revised EPBD and harmonizing its efforts with broader EU strategies such as Fitfor55. Beyond immediate implementation, EPBD.wise seeks to establish a replicable model, one that supports ongoing EU legislation implementation, achieved through close collaboration with stakeholders, network agencies, and national partners.

Delving into the specifics, the NBRP is a cornerstone of this endeavor, aiming to chart a comprehensive course for national strategies in building renovation. Meanwhile, the MEPS constitutes a critical benchmark for ensuring the minimum energy performance of buildings. Simultaneously, the EPC, acting as a transparent indicator, plays a pivotal role in the overall effort, providing a clear picture of a building's energy performance. In essence, EPBD.wise endeavors to not only meet short-term targets but also lay the groundwork for sustainable and adaptable policies that stand the test of time, contributing significantly to the EU's overarching energy and climate ambitions. The **focus countries** (FC) decided on in the project are **Hungary, Ukraine, Bulgaria, Greece, Poland, and Romania**.

- **WP1: Project Management and Coordination – TU WIEN**
 - **Objective:** The comprehensive management of the project, aiming to ensure efficient coordination, adherence to budget and timeline, and achievement of project goals. Key objectives include facilitating communication among partners, handling financial and administrative aspects, ensuring quality control, organizing regular meetings, managing project risks, and reporting to contracting authorities. Expected outcomes encompass the project's document repository, periodic reporting, meeting minutes, data management plan, and reporting on gender inclusivity.
- **WP2: Target Setting and Planning (ZEB and NBRP) – TU WIEN**
 - **Objective:** Initiating building stock improvement requires setting targets, a crucial aspect of implementing the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD). EPBD outlines two key instruments: defining zero-emission buildings (ZEB) and developing national building renovation plans (NBRPs). The ZEB standard significantly influences future building stock targets and impacts the design of related instruments (WP3-5). NBRPs, essential for national target setting and renovation planning, replace Long-term Renovation Strategies in the recast EPBD. The objectives include examining links between ZEB definitions and EPBD implementation, reviewing proposed ZEB definitions, analyzing good practice examples, creating a policy guideline for target setting and NBRP drafting, and preparing for replication in other EU Member States. The outcome aims to provide an overview of ZEB definitions, NBRPs, and policy guidelines for effective target planning implementation.
- **WP3: Minimum Energy Performance Standards (MEPS) – E-THINK**
 - **Objective:** The objectives involve gathering policy needs for implementing Minimum Energy Performance Standards (MEPS), analyzing relevant good practice examples, and crafting a policy guideline document to enhance the effective implementation of MEPS. The ultimate goal is to lay the groundwork for replicating this approach, resulting in an overview of MEPS policy needs and the current status, specific policy guidelines for MEPS implementation in focus countries, and broader guidelines applicable across all European Union Member States.
- **WP4: Building Renovation Passport (BRP) – SERA**
 - **Objective:** The objectives entail gathering policy needs for implementing Building Renovation Programs (BRP), analyzing relevant good practice examples, and creating a policy guideline document to enhance effective BRP implementation. The aim is to establish a foundation for replicating this approach, resulting in an overview of BRP policy needs and the current status, specific policy guidelines for BRP implementation in focus countries, and broader guidelines applicable across all European Union Member States.
- **WP5: Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) – ADENE**

- **Objective:** The objectives include gathering and mapping needs for optimal management and enhancement of existing Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) schemes, analyzing pertinent good practice examples, and formulating a policy guideline for effectively utilizing EPC schemes in specific countries. The intended outcome is to pave the way for replicating this approach, resulting in an overview of EPC policy needs and the current status, guidelines for optimal management and improvement of EPCs in focus countries, and broader guidelines applicable across all European Union Member States.
- **WP6:** Effective Implementation of Policy Packages: Securing Consistency and Concepts for Monitoring, Reporting, and Evaluation – BPIE
 - **Objective:** WP6 is dedicated to supporting the implementation of WP2-5, ensuring these policies complement each other and yield the anticipated outcomes. Its close integration with WP2-5 necessitates ongoing collaboration with involved partners. The objectives encompass ensuring a uniform approach to policy design across WP2-5, identifying synergies with Fitfor55 provisions relevant to EU building stock decarbonization, and addressing connections between EPBD and other EU policies/strategies and emerging trends in the building industry. The anticipated results include providing specific guidance to Member States on effectively designing, monitoring, and evaluating policies under EPBD, thereby avoiding gaps in policy design.
- **WP7:** Stakeholder Engagement, Communication, Dissemination and Sustainability, Replication, and Networking with Other LIFE Projects – BPIE
 - **Objective:** The project aims to develop a comprehensive Communication, Dissemination, and Stakeholder Engagement plan, guiding effective communication throughout and beyond the project's duration. This plan seeks to involve key stakeholders, ensure the uptake of project results in focus countries, and widely publicize achievements across the EU. Additionally, the project aims to manage stakeholder engagement activities strategically, emphasizing community building at the Member State level, particularly in focus countries. Efforts include shaping narratives on EPBD implementation and building renovation in focus country and EU media, raising awareness of implementation solutions and best practices. The project also plans to create synergies with other LIFE projects, fostering consistent dissemination to a broader EU policy audience and facilitating result replication in other Member States. Lastly, an Exploitation Plan will be developed to ensure the effective and direct utilization of project results post-project.

Information on the model to be used

The Invert/EE-Lab is a comprehensive techno-socio-economic bottom-up building stock model that simulates energy-related investment decisions in buildings, specifically focusing on space heating, hot water generation, and space cooling end-uses.² Invert/EE-Lab is based on a highly disaggregated description of the building stocks in the different countries of the EU (+ Iceland, Norway, Switzerland, UK), including building type, age, state of renovation, existing heating systems, user structure as well as regional elements such as availability of energy infrastructure, e.g., district heating or natural gas on a sub-country level. The Invert/EE-Lab model simulates investment decisions in the building shell and the heat supply and distribution systems through a combination of a discrete choice approach and technology diffusion theory. It is a myopic simulation tool that considers the effects of different policy decisions, such as economic incentives, research, and technology development, on the total energy demand, energy carrier mix, reductions, and costs for included end-uses.³ The model has been involved in over 40 projects in EU-27+ countries for over ten years and continues to be a valuable tool for

² Op.europa.eu. 2022. Renewable space heating under the revised Renewable Energy Directive : ENER/C1/2018-494 : final report.. [online] Available at: <<https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/16710ac3-eac0-11ec-a534-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>> [Accessed 27 June 2022].

³ Kranzl, L., Aichinger, E., Büchele, R., Forthuber, S., Hartner, M., Müller, A., Toleikyte, A., 2018. Are scenarios of energy demand in the building stock in line with Paris targets? Energy Effic. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12053-018-9701-1>

policymakers, researchers, and industry professionals in the field of energy efficiency and building technology.⁴

⁴Müller, A., 2015. Energy Demand Assessment for Space Conditioning and Domestic Hot Water: A Case Study for the Austrian Building Stock (PhD-Thesis). Technische Universität Wien, Wien.

1. Data description

1a Lists of datasets that will be reused or produced

Produced datasets

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	EPBD.wise_LTRS documents overview.xlsx	Standard office documents	xlsx	100 MB	no
P2	EPBD.wise_081223_Template for mapping policy needs_HU.docx	Standard office documents	docx	100 MB	no
P3	EPBD.wise_081223_Template for mapping policy needs_RO.docx	Standard office documents	docx	100 MB	no
P4	EPBD.wise_081223_Template for mapping policy needs_UA.docx	Standard office documents	docx	100 MB	no
P5	EPBD.wise_081223_Template for mapping policy needs_EL.docx	Standard office documents	docx	100 MB	no

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P6	EPBD.wise_081223_Template for mapping policy needs_BG.docx	Standard office documents	docx	100 MB	no
P7	EPBD.wise_081223_Template for mapping policy needs_PL.docx	Standard office documents	docx	100 MB	no
P8	Invert_EE-Lab_eff_high_dh_ab_pyam_upload_file_2019_2050_resaped.csv	Structured text, Plain text	csv	100 MB	no
P9	Invert_EE-Lab_eff_high_elec_ab_pyam_upload_file_2019_2050_resaped.csv	Structured text, Plain text	csv	100 MB	no
P10	Invert_EE-Lab_eff_high_behaviour_elec_ab_pyam_upload_file_2019_2050_resaped.csv	Structured text, Plain text	csv	100 MB	no
P11	Invert_EE-Lab_eff_high_h2_ab_pyam_upload_file_2019_2050_resaped.csv	Structured text, Plain text	csv	100 MB	no
P12	Invert_EE-Lab_eff_moderate_h2_ab_pyam_upload_file_2019_2050_resaped.csv	Structured text, Plain text	csv	100 MB	no
P13	Invert_EE-Lab_eff_moderate_elec_ab_pyam_upload_file_2019_2050_resaped.csv	Structured text, Plain text	csv	100 MB	no

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P14	Invert_EE-Lab_eff_moderate_dh_ab_pyam_upload_file_2019_2050_resaped.csv	Structured text, Plain text	csv	100 MB	no

1b Data generation and reuse

Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

Within the project, we are dealing with a total of **fourteen datasets**, each serving specific purposes.

One dataset, formatted as an **MS Excel** file, is the result of an exhaustive **literature review process**. This dataset compiles information from existing reports, papers, and projects related to Long-Term Renovation Strategies (LTRS), Minimum Energy Performance Standards (MEPS), Building Renovation Passports (BRPs), and Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs). The Excel file systematically organizes the findings from this literature review, providing a comprehensive overview.

Six datasets, formatted as **MS Word** files, will be curated through a **methodical surveying approach**. These datasets are designed to capture qualitative data, outlining the nuanced policy needs for each of our focus countries: Hungary, Ukraine, Bulgaria, Greece, Poland, and Romania. By leveraging the survey responses, we aim to gain valuable insights into the specific policy requirements unique to each focus country.

Seven datasets, meticulously formatted as CSV files, are set to be generated in the later stages of the project. These datasets will stem from distinct scenarios formulated to guide focus countries in aligning with targets set by the EU Commission. To facilitate this process, we will employ an advanced demand-side building stock model known as Invert/EE-Lab. This model specializes in simulating energy-related investment decisions in buildings, with a particular focus on space heating, hot water generation, and space cooling. The numerical results from these **simulations** will be documented in CSV files, offering detailed data on energy demand, renovation requirements, and related metrics for the selected countries.

This structured approach ensures clarity, accessibility, and technical rigor in generating and managing datasets throughout the project's lifecycle, facilitating robust data analysis and comprehensive reporting.

2. Documentation and data quality

2a Data organisation, metadata, and documentation

The respective work package leaders will handle the structure and versioning of the research data.

We will be using the following domain-specific metadata standards: **EERAdata**.⁵ This will help others identify, discover, and reuse our data. The EERAdata Metadata Creator supports us in creating a standardized metadata file in a machine-readable format for our data object. It comes up with a simple standard metadata schema following Dublin Core. We decided to use this tool to use our energy modeling community standards. **Metadata is provided in both the TUhost and the project's GitHub repository.**

As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

1. Comprehensive Documentation: We will implement a comprehensive documentation strategy to ensure clarity and transparency throughout the data analysis process.

2. Metadata and Code Documentation: We commit to creating detailed metadata for all datasets, including information on variables, units, and any data transformations.

⁵ https://eeradata-platform.eu/wordpress/?page_id=2547

3. Version Control: A version control system, Github, will be employed to track changes in both data and code. This approach ensures transparency and facilitates validation and reproducibility.

4. Readme Files: Each dataset and analysis script will include readme files providing a quick overview of the dataset's structure and context, enhancing user understanding.

5. Data Dictionary: We will develop a comprehensive data dictionary for each dataset, offering a detailed guide to variable definitions, permissible values, and any special considerations.

6. Data Reuse Guidelines: Guidelines for data reuse will be provided, outlining permissible use cases, potential limitations, and any specific conditions associated with data reuse.

7. User-Friendly Formats: Documentation will be presented in user-friendly formats to cater to both technical and non-technical users, ensuring accessibility and ease of use. By incorporating these measures into our data management strategy, we aim to uphold the principles of transparency, reproducibility, and accessibility in our research data.

2b Data quality control

Several rigorous data quality checks will be conducted to ensure the reliability and accuracy of the information. These checks will encompass a thorough examination of data entry, validating the correctness and completeness of the entered data. Additionally, data representation will adhere to controlled vocabularies, contributing to consistency and standardization across the datasets. This meticulous approach to data quality assurance is imperative in upholding the integrity and trustworthiness of the project's datasets, aligning with best practices in data management.

3. Storage and backup during the research process

3a Storage and backup facilities

For the project's duration, the project manager will ensure data storage and backup in cooperation with the responsible representative of TU.it. The infrastructure of TU Wien will be used for this purpose.

- P1 (EPBD.wise_LTRS documents overview.xlsx),
- P2 (EPBD.wise_081223_Template for mapping policy needs_HU.docx),
- P3 (EPBD.wise_081223_Template for mapping policy needs_RO.docx),
- P4 (EPBD.wise_081223_Template for mapping policy needs_UA.docx),
- P5 (EPBD.wise_081223_Template for mapping policy needs_EL.docx),
- P6 (EPBD.wise_081223_Template for mapping policy needs_BG.docx),
- P7 (EPBD.wise_081223_Template for mapping policy needs_PL.docx),
- P8 (Invert_EE-Lab_eff_high_dh_ab_pyam_upload_file_2019_2050_resaped.csv),
- P9 (Invert_EE-Lab_eff_high_elec_ab_pyam_upload_file_2019_2050_resaped.csv),
- P10 (Invert_EE-Lab_eff_high_behaviour_elec_ab_pyam_upload_file_2019_2050_resaped.csv),
- P11 (Invert_EE-Lab_eff_high_h2_ab_pyam_upload_file_2019_2050_resaped.csv),
- P12 (Invert_EE-Lab_eff_moderate_h2_ab_pyam_upload_file_2019_2050_resaped.csv),
- P13 (Invert_EE-Lab_eff_moderate_elec_ab_pyam_upload_file_2019_2050_resaped.csv),
- P14 (Invert_EE-Lab_eff_moderate_dh_ab_pyam_upload_file_2019_2050_resaped.csv)

The above datasets and related metadata will be stored in TUhost: TUhost is a central and highly available TU.it virtualization platform hosted on VMware. TU.it will provide hardware, storage, and backup; our institute will be responsible for the server operation.

3b Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies listed in the introduction of this document. At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any

sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien (Verena Dolovai), and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	reading only	reading only
P2	writing	reading only	reading only
P3	writing	reading only	reading only
P4	writing	reading only	reading only
P5	writing	reading only	reading only
P6	writing	reading only	reading only
P7	writing	reading only	reading only
P8	writing	reading only	reading only
P9	writing	reading only	reading only
P10	writing	reading only	reading only
P11	writing	reading only	reading only
P12	writing	reading only	reading only
P13	writing	reading only	reading only
P14	writing	reading only	reading only

All incidents will be handled individually by an incident response team that is maintaining the affected service.

4. Legal and ethical requirements

4a Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien (Verena Dolovai), and the DMP will be updated.

4b Intellectual property rights and ownership

There are no legal restrictions on the processing and disclosure of our data.

4c Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.

5. Data sharing and long-term preservation

5a Data publication and access conditions

As far as possible, obtained datasets will be published in repositories. Details on access conditions, reuse licenses, reasons for restrictions, etc., are collected in the table below.

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open		2026-06-29	TU Wien Research Data		CC BY-NC 4.0
P2	Open		2026-06-29	TU Wien Research Data		CC BY-NC 4.0
P3	Open		2026-06-29	TU Wien Research Data		CC BY-NC 4.0
P4	Open		2026-06-29	TU Wien Research Data		CC BY-NC 4.0
P5	Open		2026-06-29	TU Wien Research Data		CC BY-NC 4.0
P6	Open		2026-06-29	TU Wien Research Data		CC BY-NC 4.0
P7	Open		2026-06-29	TU Wien Research Data		CC BY-NC 4.0
P8	Open		2026-06-29	TU Wien Research Data		CC BY-NC 4.0
P9	Open		2026-06-29	TU Wien Research Data		CC BY-NC 4.0

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P10	Open		2026-06-29	TU Wien Research Data		CC BY-NC 4.0
P11	Open		2026-06-29	TU Wien Research Data		CC BY-NC 4.0
P12	Open		2026-06-29	TU Wien Research Data		CC BY-NC 4.0
P13	Open		2026-06-29	TU Wien Research Data		CC BY-NC 4.0
P14	Open		2026-06-29	TU Wien Research Data		CC BY-NC 4.0

The repositories used in this project are described in the following paragraph:

TU Wien Research Data is an institutional repository of TU Wien that enables the storage, sharing, and publishing of digital objects, in particular, research data. It facilitates the funders' requirements for open access to research data and the FAIR principles by making research output findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. A DOI is assigned to each dataset published in TU Wien Research Data. This service is developed by the TU Wien Center for Research Data Management and hosted by TU.it. <https://researchdata.tuwien.at/>

Here is the URL for the related TU Wien Research Data: <https://doi.org/10.70124/8r4yf-hqa78> (this link will be activated after the review process).⁶ In the meantime, you can access the GitHub repository of the project from here: <https://github.com/ozerece/EPBD.wise/>

⁶ Özer, F. E. (2023). EPBD.wise_Datasets (1.0.0) [Data set]. TU Wien. <https://doi.org/10.70124/8r4yf-hqa78>

5b Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)	foreseeable research uses and/or users
P1	TU Wien Research Data	10 years	The primary audience for the data encompasses national governments and policymakers. The data holds significance for these stakeholders as it serves as a guide for public authorities in formulating, executing, and assessing relevant instruments. The overarching aim is to adopt a comprehensive approach in accordance with the EPBD recast, while concurrently aligning with EU strategies, such as Fitfor55.
P2	TU Wien Research Data	10 years	
P3	TU Wien Research Data	10 years	
P4	TU Wien Research Data	10 years	
P5	TU Wien Research Data	10 years	
P6	TU Wien Research Data	10 years	
P7	TU Wien Research Data	10 years	
P8	TU Wien Research Data	10 years	
P9	TU Wien Research Data	10 years	
P10	TU Wien Research Data	10 years	
P11	TU Wien Research Data	10 years	
P12	TU Wien Research Data	10 years	
P13	TU Wien Research Data	10 years	
P14	TU Wien Research Data	10 years	

6. RDM responsibilities and resources

6a RDM-roles and responsibilities

Lukas Kranzl will direct the data management process overall, with the research assistant (Ece Özer) responsible for ensuring metadata production, day-to-day cross-checks, backups and other quality control activities are maintained.

6b Resources

While a dedicated budget for this particular aspect was not explicitly specified, it is implicitly covered within the General Assembly (GA) budget. The budget allocated for Work Package 1 (WP1), which includes the Data Management Plan (DMP), encompasses the necessary resources. It's important to note that this budget is integrated with other management tasks, making it challenging to delineate specific allocations solely for this purpose.

Cost name	Cost type	Description	Unit	Value
Estimated total costs				0